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Industrial and Energy Policies for Biogas-Based Electricity from Municipal Solid Waste in Brazil

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Abstract¹: Biogas, a mixture of carbon dioxide and methane resulting from the degradation of organic waste, has received increasing attention by decision makers in Brazil in recent years. Appropriate industrial and energy policies are now required to increase the still small share of this fuel in the country’s energy supply. These policies should take into account the diverse socioeconomic features concerning solid waste generation, recovery and final disposal found in the country. In the Brazilian northeastern region, for instance, the focus has been the construction of sanitary landfills and the eventual recovery of the biogas produced, while in the more developed southeastern regions specialized biogas plants fed by waste previously sorted by manual-mechanical means have been privileged. The value chain of the “biogas to energy” industry from municipal solid waste (MSW) is discussed in this paper, aiming at providing subsidies for industrial and energy policies suitable to tackle this diversity of situations.

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1 - Introduction

Biogas use for electricity production is not new in Brazil. The first commercial plants started in the 1970s as part of a plethora of initiatives aimed at reducing oil dependence following the 1973 and 1979 oil shocks. Interest in the technology waned after that, but was rekindled with the advent of the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). Through this mechanism, developed countries signatories to the Convention can buy carbon credits issued from emission reduction projects in developing countries. Projects that capture and flare biogas from sanitary landfills (or use it to produce electricity) are eligible for receiving carbon credits which can then be sold in the market. The mechanism helped to finance the three largest landfill gas-to-electricity projects in Brazil: Bandeirantes and São João in the state of São Paulo and Salvador in the state of Bahia.

With the crash of the main carbon markets at the end of the 2000 decade, interest in biogas for electricity production diminished once more. But this time, this reduced attention has been very short-lived. In recent years, more and more actors from across the country and from government, the private sector and academia have highlighted the vast untapped potential existing in the country in biogas use from a variety of sources, such as sanitary landfills, manure, etc. The reasons are manifold and include the advances of the National Policy on Solid Wastes (NPSW), the professionalization and technological upgrading of waste management companies and the rising concern of Brazilian society in increasing the use of new renewable sources of energy.

Despite this renewed interest in the sector, policies to foster technologies and practices that use biogas as a source of energy for electricity production are largely inexistent. This paper addresses options to foster the use of biogas from MSW. In the following section, waste management practices in Brazil are discussed. The third section presents current electricity production from biogas and the fourth section assesses current biogas policies. The fifth and sixth sections close the paper exposing, respectively, the methodology adopted in the research project carried out by the authors of this paper and their policy proposals for fostering the biogas-to-electricity sector in the country.

2 - Municipal solid waste management in Brazil

Like in most developing nations, there is still much to do for a good waste management in Brazil, especially in what concerns treatment and final disposal. To date, 90.4% of the waste generated in the country is collected by companies working for local authorities and given some kind of disposal. Despite this widespread collection, 37.9% of the Brazilian municipal solid waste (MSW) still finds itself disposed of in an

inadequate manner, either in open or in “controlled” landfills. Usually the practices adopted locally reflect the economic development of the region, with the richer South and Southeastern regions adopting better management practices than the poorer North, Northeast and Center-West. Furthermore, while aluminum cans, PET plastic bottles and paper are recycled in percentages of, respectively, 97.9%, 58.9% and 45.7%, the vast majority of Brazilian MSW ends up in sanitary landfills (Abrelpe, 2013).

The National Policy on Solid Wastes (NPSW), voted into law in 2010, provides the legal basis for waste management in the country. Previously, the sector was subject to various municipal MSW legislations and dealt with nationally by the legislation on environmental crimes of 1998. This law, for instance, banned all open and controlled landfills, but was not very successful in this endeavor. The new legislation which came into force is considered a significant step forward in the sector. It proposes the creation of common, inter-municipal, solutions for waste management, the permanent extinction of open landfills, electricity generation from biogas and the strengthening of “waste-pickers” cooperatives. It gained considerable notoriety following the 2014 deadline for the end of open landfills in the country. The missed deadline, as well as attempts, through the National Congress, of postponing it, gained widespread media attention. Whether this will continue in the long term is still to be seen.

Despite the advances achieved so far, there are still many difficulties ahead. Institutional capacity to deal with MSW is still limited, especially in smaller municipalities. The investment of USD 44 per capita in MSW management (Abrelpe, 2013) is still short of what is needed to solve its major challenges. Representatives from this sector point out that an additional USD 1.5 billion would be necessary to close every single open and “controlled” landfill and substitute them with proper disposal and treatment practices. This is more than a 16% increase in a market worth around USD 9.2 billion. This is not an impossible amount of money to gather, but the looming economic woes in the coming years, the general shortcomings of investment in infrastructure in the country and the resistance of consumers towards paying more for waste management represent formidable obstacles.

3 - Electricity generation from MSW biogas in Brazil

Electric power generation in Brazil is quite diverse and, unlike the majority of countries in the world, it generates most of its power from renewable sources. Hydroelectricity represents 66.9% of the total installed capacity in the country – 132,789 MW. Adding to this figure the 10,503 MW from sugarcane bagasse, 4,562 MW from wind power and 609 MW from various other renewable sources, such as photovoltaic stations, elephant grass, charcoal and wood residues, the renewable share of electricity in the total installed capacity jumps to 78.7% (ANEEL, 2014).

The electric power sector in Brazil has been dominated during decades by a mindset that privileges large power generation projects, usually located far away from major consuming areas. This is changing given two recent trends, common to most countries in the world.

First, the costs of renewable generation of electricity are rapidly falling. Wind and sugarcane bagasse, both competitive sources of electricity generation in the country, have had considerable reductions in installation and operational costs, whereas coal and nuclear power have witnessed the opposite effect (WWF-Brasil, 2012).

The second trend is the growing interest in microgeneration, “the production of energy on the level of individual buildings or local communities” (Praetorius, Sauter and Watson, 2008). A 2012 resolution from ANEEL, the Brazilian electricity regulatory agency, established the general conditions concerning the grid access for micro generation (less than 100 kW) and mini generation (between 100 kW and 1 MW) of electricity from hydro, solar, wind and biomass sources, including co-generation (ANEEL, 2012). So far, as of April 2014, the projects have been few, totaling around 2 MW of capacity recently installed, but expectations are high for future growth (Mattar, 2014).

MSW biogas is still a very timid source of power in Brazil, with only 73 MW of installed capacity, representing 0.0006% of the total. The largest share (90.4%) comes from landfill biogas, located in the southeastern part of the country (states of São Paulo, SP, and Minas Gerais, MG). Biogas from sewage treatment follows suit with 5.4%, while biogas from rural activities ranks third with 4.2%. As of today, there are a total of 8 landfills using biogas for electricity production, as can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 – Electricity Generation Plants from Landfill Biogas

Plant	Owner	City	Installed Capacity (kW)	Total Percent
São João Biogás Salvador	São João Energia Ambiental S/A	São Paulo - SP	24.640	37,3 %
Bandeirantes	Termoverde Salvador S.A.	Salvador - BA	19.730	29,8 %
Asja BH	Biogas Energia Ambiental S.A.	São Paulo - SP	5.000	7,6 %
CTR Juiz de Fora	Consórcio Horizonte Asja	Belo Horizonte - MG	4.278	6,5 %
Guatapar	Valorgas – Energia e Biogs Ltda	Juiz de Fora - MG	4.278	6,5 %
Uberlndia	Guatapar Energia S.A.	Guatapar - SP	4.278	6,5 %
Itaja Biogs	Energas Gerao de Energia Ltda	Uberlndia - MG	2.852	4,3%
Total	Itaja Biogs e Energia S.A.	Curitiba - PR	1.065	1,6 %
			66.121	100%

Source: ANEEL (2014)

Despite its small size, the sector is expanding considerably fast: 20 MW of electricity generation capacity in Barueri (state of São Paulo) is under construction, while 70 MW are planned throughout the country, but with construction not yet started (ANEEL, 2014). All these facilities will more than double the current electricity production from MSW biogas.

4 – Current policies supporting electricity generation from biogas in Brazil

Policies to support certain forms of electricity generation can take a variety of forms. Demand policies, for instance, foster demand by requiring power distributors to buy pre-specified amounts of electricity from certain sources, the added costs being diluted among their many customers. Alternatively, the government can set a cap on an important variable, such as greenhouse gas emissions, letting the market decide how to best allocate resources and share the additional costs.

Supply policies work on the opposite end of the value chain, helping equipment producers, power generators or plant operators through a variety of means. They either speed up the development of certain technologies, making them cheaper and more accessible, or contribute to project's profitability indicators through subsidies or credit at lower interest rates.

Finally, “cross-cutting” policies work throughout the value chain and seldom act as a stand-alone solution. Working in tandem with other government initiatives, these types of policies disseminate information to interested entrepreneurs, companies or communities regarding the benefits and challenges of adopting certain technologies to manage waste or generate electricity. They also support information exchange between different agents by aiding the establishment of networks, give training on the market and technological aspects of specific technologies and foster better community understanding and acceptance of them.

Contrary to what happens in places such as Europe or the United States, the current structure of the biogas sector in Brazil owes much to international factors, notably the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) of the UNFCCC (see Figure 1). This was the only demand inducing policy for biogas up to 2014, when the government, interested in fostering biogas from MSW as an energy source, included it into the 6th Energy Reserve Auction. Electricity auctions are the main tool by which the Ministry of Mines and Energy calls for new power stations and expands power supply in the country. There were no bids from potential MSW biogas generators in that energy reserve auction due to the low price-cap set by the government for this technology - 64 USD/MWh (Instituto Acende Brasil, 2014). With the low prices witnessed in the carbon markets and the failure of this auction to attract any MSW biogas projects, it can be stated that currently there are no effective demand inducing policies for biogas in Brazil.

Similarly, there are just two specific supply side policies for biogas. Biogas projects receive a discount of 100% in the tariffs for using the electricity transmission (TUST) and/or distribution (TUSD) grids (Oliveira, 2014). MSW biogas plants are also entitled to receive the tax reduction benefits from the Special Incentives Regime for the Development of Infrastructure (REIDI in the original Portuguese acronym). REIDI, created in 2007, exempts private sector projects that contribute to strategic areas of the

country’s infrastructure (transport, ports, energy, sewage and irrigation) from the payment of the PIS/Pasep and Cofins taxes (Brazil, 2007).

Figure 1 – Biogas support policies in Brazil

“Cross-cutting” initiatives in this area are better structured in Brazil, to a large extent because they are a logical first step towards assessing how to best serve this nascent sector. There are two main initiatives currently under implementation.

The first, Probiogás, is a partnership between the government of Brazil and the German international cooperation body GIZ. Started in 2013, it works in four fronts: 1) information dissemination; 2) training; 3) company and academic partnerships; and 4) technical support. Towards this goal, the project will invest €160 million, from which €50 million will be credit for projects in this area (Ciríaco de Miranda, 2014)

The second initiative is part of the U.S. led *Global Methane Initiative* (GMI), which aims at reducing 180 million tons of CO₂-equivalent methane emissions by 2015 from agriculture, coal mining, wastewater, municipal solid waste and oil&gas. 42 countries participate in this initiative, under coordination of the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). The Brazilian participation in the initiative has been fruitful with the organization of a series of information exchange conferences and seminars, as well as the development of a study that identified an existing electricity generating potential of 536 MW using biogas from sanitary landfills (Abrelpe, 2012).

Finally, the most important policy that indirectly influences this sector is the law entitled “National Policy on Solid Waste” (NPSW), presented earlier in this paper. Among its various goals and objectives, three measures will have a significant impact on MSW biogas projects. First, the law requires that the country eliminates all its open and controlled landfills, substituting them by sanitary landfills. It also specifies targets

for the use of biogas from landfills; the first of them, the installation of 50 MW of MSW biogas power plants until 2015, was already fulfilled. Finally, it sets restrictions on how much organic MSW can be sent to sanitary landfills, being used instead in biodigestors or composted (MMA, 2012). Table 2 shows the potential impacts of this law on electricity generation from MSW biogas.

Table 2 – Impacts of the National Policy on Solid Waste on electricity generation from MSW biogas in Brazil

Possible Impacts	Goal of the NPSW End of open and controlled landfills	Targets for the use of biogas from landfills	Reduction of organic MSW sent to landfills
Impact on electricity generation from landfills	Positive	Positive	Negative
Impact on electricity generation from biodigestors	-	-	Positive

5 – A research project to uncover the value chain structure and to propose new public policies to reinforce the biogas to electricity sector in Brazil

The authors of this paper are carrying out a research project in Brazil, funded by Endesa, which provided the basis for the new public policy proposals put forward in the next section. An inductive approach is adopted in this project aimed at uncovering the value chain structure, perspectives and political demands of the biogas to electricity sector from municipal solid wastes in the country. A list of organizations was generated based on a technical literature survey, searches in the world web, participation in workshops and conferences relevant to this area, as well as indications from interviewees.

Representatives from 12 organizations were interviewed between August and December 2014. The semi-structured interviews, which usually lasted between 1 and 2 hours, addressed the following topics: 1) experience with biogas to electricity technologies; 2) existing partnerships with research institutes, industry associations, government bodies or other; 3) challenges faced; 4) perspectives on the development of the sector in the coming years and decade; 5) national industry potential to supply required components and technologies to the sector; 6) new public policies necessary to strengthen the sector; 7) existing human resources; and 8) public participation, including acceptance or rejection of certain technologies. As can be seen in Table 3, the 12 organizations included companies supplying products and services along the supply chain assessed here, industry associations and government organizations. Respondents, for the most part, have many years of experience with MSW and/or biogas and are acquainted with technical, commercial, strategic and/or political issues relevant to this area.

Table 3 – Types of organizations surveyed

Types of organizations	Number of interviews
Landfill operators	3
Engineering companies and/or equipment manufacturers	5
Consultancy companies	1
Government body	1
Industry association	1
Government body dedicated to international development	1
Total	12

From these interviews, the authors were able to identify the main political demands necessary to strengthen the biogas to electricity sector in Brazil. These are discussed in the next section.

6 – Required policies to foster MSW biogas to electricity in Brazil

6.1 A bright future for sanitary landfills

Landfills will still dominate waste treatment “solutions” in the coming years and even decades in Brazil. In the Northern, Northeastern and Center portions of the country, regions where inadequate waste management options are most prevalent, the transition from their many waste dumps to sanitary landfills have to be supported by an adequate set of policies (see FADE, 2013). To begin with, public procurement and contracts should explicitly state that any new sanitary landfill will be expected to capture and use the biogas generated. This requires that government officials understand the existing technologies, their potential and limitations, as well as the opportunities they present to improve MSW management in the region. Technical visits from government officials to existing projects in Europe, North America and Asia are paramount, complemented by information exchanges and training in conferences, workshops and the like.

There is a need for training centers in Brazil dealing with the optimization of landfill operations, given the acute lack of specialized human resources in the sector. Local companies have gone around these limitations by providing training abroad, or carrying out partnerships with international corporations. Obviously, the focus has been on solving company specific issues, rather than creating a solid foundation of human resources that could aid the sector as a whole. Here, federal support, alongside international development funds, could make the most impact. Government should also support the development, already in progress, of specialized MSW management courses (at a bachelor’s and master’s degree) to provide well trained specialists with a long term strategic vision.

This sector is plagued by heavy taxation on imported technologies. Electricity generators, for instance, are notorious examples. While there are national substitutes operating at smaller scale, most companies prefer those proven generators of large multinational corporations in order to reduce operational risks. However, the level of current taxation almost doubles the price of the generators, reducing considerably the profitability (and hence private interest) for biogas-to-electricity projects. Furthermore, there is a problem of double, and even triple taxation throughout the value chain, as there is a tax on waste collection, a tax on depositing waste in landfills and finally a tax on electricity production. Streamlining taxation policies and reducing tariffs will be important to increase profitability ratios and creating the proper incentives for the private sector to generate electricity.

Feed-in tariffs will not be a reality anytime soon in Brazil, given the federal government lack of interest in them. Energy auctions, the main instrument by which the government coordinates and manages the expansion of electricity supply, will continue as the main option for the development of “new” renewable energy options (using the term found in Goldemberg, 2006). The success story of wind power and, more recently, the advances of solar power in the country are, to a large extent, due to the government’s initiative of setting high price-caps in the energy auctions. As the sector develops and costs drop, the price-caps initially set in the auctions can then be reduced. While several stakeholders believe that the government is testing the waters and will, in future auctions, propose higher price-caps for biogas from MSW and other sources, it is never too much to stress the importance of this instrument to foster this type of technology. It is the single most important instrument available for the federal government and should be used to its best effect.

6.2 Beyond Landfills – Biodigestors’ Next Wave

The National Policy on Solid Wastes requires that the amount of organics sent to landfills is gradually reduced over time. To that end, industrial composting systems and biodigestors become important technological solutions to treat organic MSW. In the richer Southern and Southeastern portions of the country, and in the few regions of larger wealth in other parts of Brazil, the focus will be on separating organic from non-organic waste and treating the organic stream. Given the relative simplicity of the technology, lower investment costs and some public misconception, systems that solely produce compost will be initially preferred over more complex ones, such as advanced biological treatment (see DEFRA, 2013), which produce both electricity and compost. Outreach activities by the government will be essential in disseminating knowledge and educating local officials on the importance of tapping into a decentralized source of electricity generation.

Contrary to technologies used in sanitary landfills, which are largely established, biodigestor technologies are still under development in Brazil. While there are many

industrial initiatives, companies that are developing biodigestors specifically adapted to local climates and the characteristics of local MSW choose to play their cards very close to their chest, foregoing opportunities to exchange lessons learned. While “safe” idea exchange encounters are a possibility, the more important initiative by the government will likely be a targeted technology development policy, not dissimilar to foreign experiences, such as the STUB in Denmark. The STUB and later initiatives that came out of it allowed the country to develop and continuously improve those biogas technologies most adequate to the socioeconomic realities of the country (Raven and Gregersen, 2007).

This technological policy should encourage strong relationships between research institutions and the private sector. All the companies interviewed mentioned their wish to engage in such partnership, or stressed their on-going partnerships. While the process is not always smooth, these types of partnerships are essential for technology development. Government can foster more of them through existing institutions such as FINEP, the main body responsible for the public financing of innovations in the country. The establishment of stronger social networks of research institutions, government and the private sector, a by-product of such policies, will reinforce existing processes of knowledge sharing and learning by all stakeholders.

6.3 Integrated solutions for large urban areas

Landfills require a large amount of space. Few, if any, large urban sprawls have the luxury of an abundance of land, making landfills an economically unattractive option in the long run. This is a particularly important for São Paulo, the largest Brazilian city, home to around 19 million inhabitants. Both the Bandeirantes and São João landfills closed, having exhausted the amount of MSW they can absorb, and the city now depends solely on the Caieiras landfill. There are very few other options available to the city and serious steps, already under way, need to be implemented in order to foster a proper treatment of the city’s solid waste, leaving the landfill as a last resort.

To this end, an integrated approach is in order and will include a host of different technologies including mechanical and manual waste separation, biological treatment (for compost and energy), creation of refuse derived fuel (RDF) for energy purposes, and the recycling of paper, metals, glass and plastics. Large municipalities usually have dedicated and well-trained professionals with the authority and skills needed to implement and manage such a large scale scheme. Furthermore, their knowledge of the local terrain is indispensable for stakeholder buy-in, negotiations with technology providers, management of relationships with private partners, among others.

Large municipalities will benefit greatly from national policies that strengthen the sector as a whole, as well as the increased professionalization of companies operating therein. Higher prices for electricity from biogas or technological development, densely populated Brazilian municipalities will benefit from both. Nonetheless, there is one

specific policy that will aid them in their work and that is funding. MSW management schemes such as these are notoriously expensive and, while many cities are able to increase tariffs for MSW management (due to their relative larger wealth, in comparison to small cities), the federal government must step in to contribute to the initial capital investment. This is particularly important given that the National Policy on Solid Waste attributes many responsibilities to municipalities, but is mute on how they can access resources to implement their MSW management.

7 - Conclusion

This paper proposes a few energy and industrial policies necessary to strengthen the generation of electricity from biogas of municipal solid wastes. It is stressed throughout the article that regions will benefit differently according to their specific socioeconomic realities.

The northern, center and northeastern portions of Brazil, for instance, will concentrate their investment towards increasing the number of sanitary landfills and reducing open dumps and other means of inadequate MSW treatment. They will benefit greatly from policies aimed at rationalizing taxation of imported equipment (especially the generators), training landfill operators and government officials and, most importantly, warranting higher electricity prices in the country's energy auctions. The southern and southeastern portions of the country, where the introduction of biodigestors will gain progressively more importance for MSW treatment, should profit from policies that foster technological development and communicate the benefits of biogas as a decentralized source of electricity for the municipalities' energy needs. Finally, large urban centers such as São Paulo or Rio de Janeiro need access to proper amounts of funds to reduce the capital costs needed to implement large scale multi-technology solutions to the enormous quantity of waste they generate.

There is evidently much to be done in the country, but recent developments such as the professionalization of the sector, the launching of the National Solid Waste Policy, the increased interest in biogas use and the demand for more sustainable solutions to many of our modern day woes give cause for optimism.

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